

ORION | Trapezium

A Monthly Publication of the ORION Astronomical Society

Comet C/2025 A6 Lemmon, imaged by Don Spong at TAO on the evening of Monday Nov. 3, 2025, using a Celestron Edge HD telescope and a ZWO533MCPro camera. The comet was in Ophiuchus, visual magnitude *ca.* 4.8, at a distance of 0.87 AU from Earth. This is a stack of ~100 30-second frames.

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Page Three Astronomy

Astrocamera Safety Net:

Here's a remarkably good idea in action. Suppose your valuable high-quality astrocamera is attached to the end of your telescope by an extension tube to allow it to focus. During a long slew the one or two feeble screws that hold it in position may loosen, and your camera will fall to the concrete pad. This happened to the Court Astronomer. But no more! With a simple \$2 mesh net enclosure with drawstring, here attached to the OTA as a backup, your camera will now only fall into a net. The picture at right is from one such event, on 12-13 Oct 2025.

The **ORION Astronomical Society** is a science and astronomy group founded in April 1974 by scientists from the United States Department of Energy facilities at Oak Ridge, Tennessee. We primarily serve the communities of Oak Ridge and Knoxville and the counties of Anderson, Knox, and Roane.

ORION's mission is to support scientific research, teaching, and astronomical activities in East Tennessee. We hold monthly public meetings at the Oak Ridge RSCC Campus, and are active at Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO), hosting public events, sharing knowledge of the skies, and helping to provide intellectually stimulating programs. ORION works to share the wonders of the cosmos and the culture of science.

ORION members include scientists, engineers, technicians, IT experts, artists, students, and others with varied talents and expertise. Over half of ORION members own telescopes, many are amateur radio operators, and some have expertise in astrophotography.

ORION has working relationships with several organizations, including museums and other amateur astronomy groups. Membership is open to individuals who will actively contribute their time and ideas. The annual membership fee is \$20, and student discounts are available. There is no charge for our newsletters and publications, or for participation in most ORION activities.

ORION Board and Officers:

President: Don Spong

VP and Program Chair: David Fields

Secretary, IT: Rob Fowler

Treasurer: Bob Edwards

Editor: Ted Barnes

ORION Speaker POC: Richard Piety

Member w/o Portfolio: Art Allison

TRAPEZIUM is a monthly publication of the ORION Astronomical Society. The issue date is the Friday preceding the monthly ORION meeting, chosen to provide timely information regarding the planned Program.

From March 2025 we have attempted to produce a somewhat shorter version of the Trapezium, which would still include important information regarding the monthly ORION presentation, as well as information regarding Public Stargazes and other notable events relating to ORION and TAO. The information removed includes a list of the brighter active supernovae, an observers' equipment section, and personal "Meet ORION" mini-biographies. However we concluded that some components, such as a separate Astrophotography section, are so important for a publication on amateur astronomy that one really cannot justify excluding them. So, the new Trapezium is only somewhat shorter, by about 20 pages.

Messages from ORION

President's Message

- Don Spong

We're getting into the winter viewing season, with crisp, cool weather and hopefully clear skies. Orion and the Pleiades are some of the most popular viewing objects this time of year. Who knows, maybe this will be the winter when we'll get to see the red supergiant Betelgeuse finally go supernova. Keep your eyes peeled. We still also have a plethora of interesting comets to keep track of, including the mysterious and controversial 3I/ATLAS.

November 6 is the full moon (Beaver moon – this is when beavers build their shelters), and the new moon will be on November 20, with November 22-23 a good dark sky weekend. A variety of planets are now visible, including Neptune, Saturn, Jupiter and Uranus. Saturn's rings are very edge-on and narrow – they will not be that way again for another 15 years. The sun continues to be at solar maximum. November meteor showers include the Taurids (November 11 – 12) and the Leonids (November 16 – 17); however, the moon may still be fairly bright for the Taurids.

We have quite a number of comets to look for: C/2025 A6 Lemmon, C/2025 R3 Swan, 3I/ATLAS (back in the northern hemisphere around December 5), C/2025 K1 ATLAS in Leo (magnitude 10.5) and 210P/Christensen in Libra (magnitude 11.8). Deep space objects of interest for November include Andromeda (M31) and its two companions, (M32 and M110); the Veil Nebula in Cygnus; the North American Nebula (NGC 7000); the Blinking Planetary Nebula (NGC 6826) in Cygnus; the Blue Snowball in Pegasus; the Helix Nebula (NGC 7293) in Aquarius; the double cluster (NGC 869 and 884) in the constellation Aquila; globular cluster M15 in Pegasus; the Ghost Nebula (Sh2-136) in Cepheus, the Pleiades (M45), the Bubble Nebula (NGC 7635) in Cassiopeia; NGC 7331 and Stephan's quintet, and finally M33 in Andromeda. I wish you clear skies and good viewing!

TAO Director's Message / Observatory Way :

The ORION Sky Ruler *

David Fields

October 2025

The photo on the left shows our new road sign for Roane State's Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO). Traveling West on Caney Creek Road from Roane County Park, the sign appears on the left just after crossing Joiner Hollow Road.

TAO Public Stargazes and Special Events

TAO offers Public Stargazes to the community on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month, weather permitting. Our usual schedule for the summer is to open at 8:30 pm and continue to nominally 10:30 pm -- later when the sky and attendance encourage this. Opening time changes according to the season, and a good guide is to arrive at the observatory about sunset, when weather is encouraging. These Stargazes are supported by local astronomy clubs, especially ORION members and friends, and benefit our students and community. Our TAO Stargazes are usually well attended, with a full classroom of visitors for evening astronomy lectures.

What are rulers and Sky Rulers? Where do we carry them?

A ruler is a tool for measurement of linear distance. Measurement can be a tool for understanding. **We can define a Sky Ruler as a tool for measuring angular separation of objects in the sky.** Let's explore the need, the history of celestial angular measurement, and possible design for a modern Sky Ruler.

In general, a ruler is useful only when it is in the hands of the user. For a hiker with a map, the ruler is in his hand with his map and compass. For a designer or engineer, the ruler is on his desk. For a medical technician, the same.

** This is a reprint of the October 2025 article.*

Observatory Way (cont.)

For an astronomer, the sky ruler must be close at hand – in his/her pocket, or hidden on a reticle in his telescope eyepiece, or be part of a computer program. Once a telescope is aligned with the sky the astronomer may rely on the computer for many things, but if there is no computer, the astronomer needs the Sky Ruler in his pocket. So, how may we obtain or design such a ruler? And how do we get it into the hands of ORION members and TAO students?

The Sky Ruler should also present physical constants, show linear measurements (inches and cm), be inexpensive so we can give away as many as we like, identify ORION as a research-oriented group of enthusiastic, fact-oriented astronomers, and delight ORION members and students.

This was the challenge I posed to our ORION board last Monday. We're still thinking about this, so let us know your suggestions. Meanwhile, here are some background thoughts.

Astronomy Rulers

This photo shows a plastic ruler that ORION gave to RSCC students and ORION members a few years ago, together with another of my favorite astronomy rulers:

The ORION ruler (above) fulfilled several purposes. It was a nice Christmas gift to ORION members and students, plus it introduced students in my Astronomy classes to the idea that 'measurements' are important. It also introduced the metric system. It was an example of how ORION helps the college, in addition to helping the students with astronomy, and introducing astronomy and the night sky at our TAO stargazes. I wished

Observatory Way (cont.)

many times that it included much more information, but we found a nice price, provided that we kept the information short and simple.

The TVIW ruler (in the image below) provided a perspective on the distance to the closest star systems, and presented some of the physical constants that define our system of units.

These were both useful rulers, but they had disadvantages. The ORION ruler was durable, but too costly to give away in large numbers. TVIW ruler was made of cheap cardboard, but the TVIW ruler was inexpensive, so many were distributed. Both were good rulers, but they did not give a sense of measuring the sky – they were not actual “Sky Rulers.”

A disadvantage of both rulers was that at a length of 6.5,” they didn’t easily fit into a shirt pocket or a wallet. What rulers might avoid these issues? Here are two examples, and I usually carry both:

Special-purpose rulers often have special functions that convert linear measures to other values, such as those for engineers (left, for a folded triangular ruler for dimensional scaling) and for medical technicians (right).

Observatory Way (cont.)

Designing a Sky Ruler for Astronomers

A Sky Ruler should permit measurements of angular distances in the sky. This would be useful to star-hop from known bright stars or Constellations. It should also present physical constants, show linear measurements (inches and cm), be inexpensive so we can give away as many as we like, identify ORION as a research-oriented group of enthusiastic, fact-oriented astronomers, and delight ORION members and students. It should stay close at hand, fitting the wallet and/or shirt pocket. Thus it might be business-card size, or it might be a 5" or 6" ruler that could be folded.

Does a "modern" astronomer need a Sky Ruler? Certainly a modern astronomer needs a 'normal' ruler for linear measurements on a star chart or across a computer screen. Then one might convert mathematically to actual distances, or to angular degrees for telescope positioning. Yes, for measurements of eyepiece holder diameter (maybe 0.96" for a valuable antique telescope), or eyepiece optical aperture, or the required length of a USB cable, or defining one of the similar computer connectors -- a ruler is a necessary tool for an astronomer.

It's not difficult to estimate angles in the sky if one knows a little trigonometry, and can do arithmetic mentally. But most beginners and students do not fit this pattern. Many amateur astronomers struggle to find objects in the sky unless they have an aligned telescope close at hand. Introducing students to the sky can be difficult without reference points and a way to scale distances. In my classes, they first learn some Constellations and bright stars. They must also learn to estimate angles, but for some this is difficult.

So yes, there is a need for a Sky Ruler. Let's discover how to include a Sky Ruler on our astronomer's kit. A most useful ruler for an astronomer would be one that measures not only linear distances, but also angular distances in the sky. The earliest such rules of thumb for sky angles were probably based on finger widths and hand spans; the angle was based on the width of the chosen finger or a span at arm's length.

Observatory Way (cont.)

The hand Sky Ruler was approximate and not useful unless one had an excellent memory or some tattoos.

Instruments were invented to measure celestial angles and to provide better reliability and accuracy than afforded by hands. These rulers had names such as cross-staff (or Jacob's staff, left illustration) and sextant (right illustration). Although useful, they do not meet our goals of low cost, reproducibility, and reasonable size.

Construction and use of a cross-staff can be both fun and instructive. (See <https://www.skyatnightmagazine.com/advice/make-a-sky-ruler>.)

Modern Celestial Angle Rulers for Astronomers

Are there any modern sky rulers in common use? My favorite, after sometimes using the apps on my iPhone (most apps are not very good for measuring angles), is the Telrad finder – a reticle-equipped star finder that shows angular size of celestial objects. The target shows circles of 3 diameters: 0.5, 2, and 4 degrees. The Telrad finder is large, and mounts on a telescope. It is an excellent tool for orienting a telescope, and is useful for angle measurements below 4 degrees.

At a cost of about \$50, and fragile, it doesn't meet our goals, but it can be a useful instrument.

Observatory Way (cont.)

A Sky Ruler for ORION

We have reached a design point for our Sky Ruler:

- Construction: Light-weight, plastic or paper, perhaps transparent
- Cost: Low
- Size: Standard business card size (to fit shirt pocket or wallet), or 5" ruler, to be folded
- Linear Distance scale: cm and probably inches
- Angular Distance scale: arc-degrees on two edges
Long edge: about 10 arc deg for standard business card held at arm's length
Short edge: about 6 arc deg for standard business card held at arm's length
- Information Included:
Physical constants from TVIW ruler
QR code for ORION and TAO
www.orioninc.org
www.roanestate.edu/obs
www.ORIONastronomy+subscribe@groups.io
Map
Oak Ridge Isochronous Observation Network on
www.astrospheric.com

Calculating angular distances between stars

This discussion has been about measurement, but if one wishes to calculate the angle between two stars from their celestial coordinates, there is a simple formula for that angle in terms of their right ascensions (RAs) and declinations (Decs). If α_1 and α_2 are the RAs and δ_1 and δ_2 the Decs of the two stars, the cosine of the angle θ between them is given by $\cos \theta = \cos \delta_1 \cos \delta_2 \cos (\alpha_2 - \alpha_1) + \sin \delta_1 \sin \delta_2$. One may evaluate θ using a table or a calculator, or by writing a simple line of code. Of course a few of the more dramatic cases could be included in an astronomy data card.

ORION Board Meetings ElCantarito

- Rob Fowler

This is a summary of topics discussed recently at the weekly (Monday 1 pm) ORION Board Meeting held as a regular working lunch at ElCantarito restaurant in Oak Ridge. Notes as contributed in Stardate format by Sec. Rob Fowler.

Stardate: 2025.03.31

In attendance were Robert Fowler, Ted Barnes, David Fields, Art Alison and Don Spong. Discussed delays on new dome report due to committee participant availability. Discussed possible going to TAO Tuesday night. Discussed next speaker is not firm for April's meeting. Discussed voting for officers at the next ORION Meeting. Discussed the next Friendship Stargaze and date for same, 8th possibly. Discussed possibly coming up with cloudy night entertainment for Friendship stargaze. Discussed Wordsworth poem about telescopes. Discussed potential security cams for TAO.

Stardate: 2025.04.07

In attendance were David Fields, Art Alison, Ted Barnes and Rob Fowler. Ted discussed the data acquired from his Arduino/LED test. David discussed a mount having the ability to track asteroids via PHD2. David discussed the Friendship Stargaze is 7:30pm Tuesday. Discussed needing pics of new concrete pads at TAO.

Stardate: 2025.04.14

In attendance were David, Ted, Art and Rob. Ted discussed results of the 785 Zwetana occultation. After a long and dramatic story, Ted revealed a successful capture. Noah is reaching out to Joe Baldwin about next month's presentation. Ted discussed quantum field theory using functional methods.

Stardate: 2025.04.21

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison, Noah Frere and Rob Fowler. Ted discussed how to use AnyDesk and log in unattended. Ted discussed a planetary occultation, Mars vs a 9th magnitude star on May 6th at 1 am. David discussed progress he is making with a Meshtastic receiver. Mention of 4 visitors who showed up at TAO and new member Kevin Wilson. David brought up calendar access .Discussed problem with rotation of glow dome lid. Watch for migration of wheel axles. One axle migrated in and caused the lid to bind.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.04.28

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison, Kevin Wilson, John Cliff and Rob Fowler. Briefly mentioned domes on CloudyNights.com. Ted discussed upcoming Mars/Star occultation and relevant challenges. HD 74058 vs Mars just after midnight 00:44 night 5th/6th morn. TAO Stargaze beginning at May 3rd 8pm. Friendship Stargaze possibly May 6th. Briefly discussed avoiding Feynman's van. Shared astrophotos. Discussed potentially going to TAO tonight & Noah's class.

Stardate: 2025.05.05

In attendance were David Fields, Art Alison, Ted Barnes, Kevin Wilson, and Rob Fowler. David asked if we have a set program for May. That remains unclear. Ted contacted Noah to confirm. We await a reply. Ted mentioned the next annual IOTA meeting is possibly going to be in New Mexico in Oct.

Stardate: 2025.05.12

At 11am David, Ted & Art met at the Library and made a first pass as setting up a display case for the club. Rob joined later. It was artistically done, decorated with a small telescope, some antique books, and astrophotos. Discussed whether Kevin might give the May lecture and what topics he has ready. He agreed to speak on the topic of stellar spectroscopy. Ted mentioned the next possible occultation on the early morning on 5/21/2025.

Stardate: 2025.05.19

In attendance were Don, David, Ted, Art, Kevin, and Rob. Kevin brought up Benjamin Baniker as a potential lecturer. Rob announced that the most recent lecture is on YouTube.

Star Date: 2025.05.26

In attendance were Don, Dave, Art & Rob. David suggested improvements to the Meade's power supply in hopes of reducing noise, higher amperage power supply, adding ferrite cores. Dave discussed getting a construction party to begin construction on the Dob shelter. Discussed parking issues at TAO.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.06.02

In attendance were Don, David, Bob, Art, Juan, Kevin and Noah (and Sunny). We met early at the library to discuss the current and new display box. Discussed meeting again, tomorrow (Tuesday). David suggested Wednesday night 8:30pm as the next Friendship Stargaze. Kevin suggested meeting at TAO to look at the Meade's encoder. Noah suggested reaching out to Gareth Davis to see if he has any potential acquaintances for another lecture. Don asked about the new dome project. David responded with a tale of woe regarding the Roane purchasing project.

Stardate: 2025.06.09

In attendance were Don, David, Art and Rob (joined by John Rather). David purchased 2 coin cells for the Celestron CGM mount. He also purchased a few ferrite cores to suppress noise from the power supply. Ted expressed an interest in having help with this months Trapezium. Discussed the new optical telescope coming online in the Atacama Desert. Briefly mentioned the library displays and Oak Ridge street lighting. Noah mentioned that Gareth Davis can give the next lecture.

Stardate: 2025.06.16

In attendance were Don, Kevin, Art and Rob. Rob showed his submission for the AMSE poster. Kevin & Don discussed PixInsight. We confirmed Kevin is speaking this month. Kevin discussed the Astronomical League and it's various programs, and contests for various achievements.

Stardate: 2025.06.23

Due to crowding at the table, no notes were taken. In attendance were Don, David, Ted, Art, Kevin and Robert.

Stardate: 2025.06.30

In attendance were David, Ted, Art, Kevin, and Rob. Don sat in for a short while. Ted & Rob discussed results of the occultation via a new process. Kevin presented a new ORION Logo. Kevin announced he will be moving out of the immediate area.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.06.30

David presented Kevin with a gift ORION T-Shirt. David brought up shop type measurements he intends to do on the Meade. The group went on discuss various theoretical topics. Mention of 4 visitors who showed up at TAO and new member Kevin Wilson David brought up calendar access. Discussed problem with rotation of glow dome lid. Watch for migration of wheel axels. One axel migrated in and caused the lid to bind.

Stardate: 2025.07.07

In attendance were Don, Ted, David, Art, Rob and visitor John Rather. Conversations opened with Ted discussing digitizing the occultation substacking project. David discussed a lightstrip project and possible application in the dome. Ted collected info for this month's Trapezium. David discussed attendance at the Sat July 5 Public Star Gaze, was 12, give or take. David discussed the testing we did on the Meade and saw no alignment errors.

Stardate: 2025.07.14

In attendance were David, Ted, Art and Rob. Ted shared some mathematical analysis of the recent occultation data. David brought up potential dates for the next Friendship Star Gaze. We discussed the next ORION lecture and whether to zoom it or not. We discussed possibly having a news feature at ORION lectures.

Stardate: 2025.07.21

In attendance were David, Don, Ted, Art, Rob... and guest John. Dave led the discussion with Rob's absence. Dave mentioned that Saturday night's public star gaze was successful, with around 8 visitors. We discussed the recent lecture and the unplanned move to the computer classroom. The general consensus is that it went well. Dave will be away on August 2nd, the next star gaze. Ted brought up details of participation in the Tuesday night / Wednesday morning occultation.

Stardate: 2025.07.28

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison and Rob Fowler We will probably have a public star gaze at TAO on 8/2/2025, public or private depending on weather and Noah's decision. 8/12/2025 Perseid meteor shower a probable star gaze.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Stardate: 2025.07.28

Our Library display will expire soon. David will inquire if we can keep it another month or if we need to clean it out this month. If it has to come down, Ted & Rob have agreed to remove the contents.

Stardate: 2025.08.04

Present were Don, Ted, Rob, Art and guest John Rather. Ted shared his most recent results and submission to IOTA that we have been re-evaluating. Don won't be present for the August ORION meeting. We believe John Cliff is August's speaker. We discussed various lightning phenomenon We also discussed the Big Bang theory and John Rather's book.

Stardate: 2025.08.11

Present were Don, Ted, David, Art, Rob and guests Richard Piety and John Rather. Ted reported on some of his recent results with IOTA's python scripts and graphing. Rob reported on visiting Lily Bluff's Star Party at Wartburg, where he met Joshua, Gareth and Owen. Don told us of a new 16 bit color astro camera he just bought, a ZWO ASI2600MCP. John told us of an experience with a pro telescope. Richard just bought a QHY174M-GPS camera for recording timed asteroid occultations. We discussed weather regarding the Perseid meteor / stargaze, 8:30pm Tuesday, but the weather is deteriorating. There is a possible occultation on 8/23/25.

Star date: 2025.08.18

In attendance were Ted, David, Art, Rob and guests John Rather and Richard Piety. David spoke to Courtney at AMSE about our ORION display. We have been invited to keep it set up for a while longer. We discussed possibly tracking 3I/ATLAS to get a pic, having an unscheduled observation evening.

Star Date: 2025.08.25

In attendance were Dave, Ted, Richard and Rob. Ted shared the results of the recent asteroid occultation. David visited the K-25 interpretive center and described the layout. He said they are interested in us bringing a star party to that location. David noticed that one of the new pads in collecting water. Rob suggested a modified a port-a-potty as a camouflage telescope cover. Calling it "Astro-Johnny: Smelling like Roses!"

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Star Date: 2025.09.01

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison and Rob Fowler. And visitor David Allred. David Fields fixed the internet with at TAO and treated several ant colonies. The skies were good from 9pm to Midnight. Discussed an upcoming eclipse in Sydney Australia in 2 years. Ted spoke to the programmer of Occult Watcher [Hristo Pavlov] who helped him troubleshoot a bug. IOTA Annual meeting is next week on zoom.

Star Date: 2025.09.08

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Rob Fowler, Don Spong, Art Alison and Richard Piety. We has a successful Moon-gaze at TAO last night. Ted discussed his occultation studies. He was successful with one last night Sunday 2025.09.07. Richard attempted it too but has not analyzed his results yet. We had a new guest last night, Art's friend Deirdre Akin. She joined the astro-luncheon as well.

Star Date: 2025.09.15

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Don Spong, Rob Fowler and Richard Piety.

- We discussed concerns over who is coordinating speakers going forward.
- Tentatively, we believe Gareth Davies is our September speaker.
- We discussed news about the cosmic interloper 3I/Atlas and new spectral data.

ORION Board Meeting at the ElCantarito Mexican Restaurant, Oak Ridge, Mon 22 Sep 2025. L to R: Ted Barnes, David Allred, David Fields, Richard Piety, Rob Fowler, and Gareth Davies.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Star Date: 2025.09.22

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Robert Fowler, Richard Piety and guest, David Alred.

Gareth Davis, Art Allison, and Don Spong arrive later.

- Ted and Richard discussed results of a recent occultation.
- Richard caught 2 new occultations recently.
- David expressed concerns over the success of last Saturday's Stargaze. He felt distracted and so thought it did not go well. But several of us thought it went very well.
- Gareth Discussed cosmic interloper 3I/Atlas, and its tail having recently turned green.
- Richard Piety confirmed that the ORION website is badly out of date.
- To support Public Star gazes, David discussed having teams of 2 to operate the Meade.
- Gareth talked about an astrophysicist, David Butler, who has a Youtube channel.

Star Date: 2025.09.29

In attendance were Don, Ted, David, Richard, Art and Robert.

- Ted told us about his visit to New Mexico and the skies at Cloudcroft.
- David asked about an abstract for October's guest speaker, Joshua from OBED.
- We discussed possibly meeting at TAO on Wednesday or Thursday.

Star Date: 2025.10.06

In attendance were David Fields, Don Spong, Ted Barnes, Rob Fowler & Art Allison.

- David suggested we create something as a giveaway to members and students. He suggested a plastic ruler to help people understand angles. He also discussed making a custom planisphere.
- We discussed using Night Sky Network to coerce dues compliance. Art took up the challenge of creating a new giveaway / print project.
- Although this month's speaker is confirmed, no details have been communicated.
- Etymology needed for the expressions "cattiewumpus" and "whackadoodle."

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Star Date: 2025.10.13

In attendance were Don Spong, Ted Barnes, David Fields, Rob Fowler and Richard Piety.

- Winter Solstice is December 21, recommending having our winter solstice party on Saturday, Dec 20th. Possible locations: High Places Church. Don also suggested El Toro, a new Mexican restaurant in Oak Ridge. There is also a Chinese buffet, Hong's Asian Bistro, near Kroger's that might be possible.
- David offered suggestions about a gift for TAO members. He showed an eclipse viewer he designed.
- We discussed problems with the Meade mount and possible solutions. We also discussed adding a guide scope.
- We discussed having a new Speaker POC and potential speaker for November. Richard volunteered to be acting Speaker POC for a while and see how it works out.

Star Date: 2025.10.20

In attendance were David, Don, Art and Rob.

- Don got a photo of Comet C/2025 R2 Swan at the recent stargaze. We had a large turnout at the star gaze because of a homeschool group. Attendance was around 30 or so.
- Rob & Ted plan to go to TAO tonight to observe a 3am occultation.
- We discussed plans for a Christmas/Solstice party. David and Don will check on the availability of 2 restaurants.
- We discussed who is the key person for each of the various ORION social media assignments.
- There is no official speaker chosen for November's meeting.

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

Star Date: 2025.10.27

In attendance were David Fields, Don Spong, Ted Barnes, Rob Fowler and Art Allison.

- Ted shared results from the most recent asteroid occultation, asteroid Chimaera.
- Considering 12/17 for the xmas party. Don & Rob shared details of 2 locations.
- David is designing a 3d joke. It's deep.

Star Date: 2025.11.03

In attendance were Dave Fields, Don Spong and Robert Fowler

- Discussed was the weather for a planned visit to TAO tonight. Agreed on a cut off of 4:30 pm to decide if weather permits.
- David showed a printable planesphere for a youth project.
- Don mentioned a new mini clamshell dome designed for small telescopes like the see-star. We also discussed how a See-Star is designed to be used remotely.
- Rob asked if we have a speaker for this coming lecture. No specific was forthcoming.

Star Date: 2025.11.11

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Richard Piety, Rob Fowler, Don Spong, and guest John Rather. Art joined late.

- We met at noon in deference to the "Lunar Flashes" zoom call at 3pm. Richard shared some general info about their mission.
- Richard also mentioned a potential speaker, Fred Schumacher.
- Ted bought a 2 inch moon filter to aid at public star gazes.
- Richard and David discussed the general state of our web presence. ORION Astronomy has a website & a facebook page and Tamke-Allan Obs also has a website & facebook page.
- We decided to go back to the bring your own beverage & covered dish for the xmas/solstice party. Possible dates? Sat 12/13.

ORION Monthly Meetings

ORION Monthly Meeting Format

Meeting Venue: City Room (A-111), just inside the main entrance, Coffey/McNalley Bldg., Oak Ridge Campus, Roane State Community College.

7:00 pm Eastern, 3rd Wednesday of each month.

Our monthly meetings (except for December, a dinner) generally proceed as follows:

- Welcome
- Announcements
- Invited Presentation and Discussion
- Awarding of the Mug
- Astrophotography / Special Presentations

The nominal start time is 7:00 pm Eastern, on the 3rd Wednesday of the month. The beginning of the meeting will usually include announcements of general interest.

Meetings typically continue until around 9:00 pm. Please plan to stay until the end. Hopefully we will all enjoy the astrophotography and other special topics discussed in the latter part of the meeting.

Remote Viewing: A live Zoom session will usually be open during the ORION Monthly Meeting, at the link:

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/88528735960?pwd=KzY4bnBHcjlhTzg3L3pOcjY0TFovUT09> or
<https://bit.ly/42apGxX>

Meeting ID: 885 2873 5960 Passcode: 716689

Title: Lunar Impact Flash Project (Recorded Zoom Meeting)

Speaker (Host): Richard Piety

ORION Meeting Speaker POC

LIF Project participant

Abstract:

How to observe Lunar Impact Flashes (LIFs)

Preparing for an observing campaign during the Geminids 2025

Lunar impact flashes (LIFs) are generated when a meteoroid, a solid object in the Solar System (typical sizes are centimeters to decimeters in diameter), hits the lunar surface at many kilometers per second and makes a small crater. Part of the energy of the impact is converted into a short flash, which can be observed with telescopes and a video camera.

The aim of this project is to gather observations of lunar impact flashes around the time of the maximum of the Geminid meteoroid stream, from 12 to 14 Dec 2025. This will help train amateur astronomers in the skills of observing Lunar Impact Flashes. It will prepare them for a citizen science program to support the ESA LUMIO CubeSat mission, due to launch in 2028. LUMIO will observe LIFs against the lunar far-side, whilst orbiting around the so-called Lagrange point, L2, of the Earth-Moon system. Earth-based telescopic observations are needed during the LUMIO mission to help compare and calibrate near and far-side impact flash rates. But it is important that we start forming observing teams now to be ready for the mission in 2 years time.

We would like as much video coverage of the night or earthshine portion of the Moon as possible from around the world, to demonstrate the useful capabilities of amateur astronomers to contribute to scientific studies.

Title: Lunar Impact Flash Project (Recorded Zoom Meeting)

Speaker (Host): Richard Piety

ORION Meeting Speaker POC

LIF Project participant

Abstract (cont.):

Because of issues with false flashes from cosmic rays, artificial objects sunglint etc., we strongly encourage simultaneous observations from widely geographically separated observers. This is an excellent way to discriminate true flashes from the noise.

The study of these impact flashes will help us to better constrain the impact rate of these small objects on the Moon. This is relevant for future human exploration of the Moon - we will want to know how many objects, and more importantly impact ejecta, might hit a Moon base, lander, rover, or a spacecraft orbiting the Moon. It is also important for science as newly formed craters have and will be discovered, that are linked to specific impact flashes.

Observing these impact flashes can be done with equipment that many amateur astronomers have access to. Impact flashes have been observed with telescopes as small as 13 cm aperture. Of course, larger aperture scopes, permit fainter (and more frequent) flashes to be detected. Successful recordings have been done with analog Wattec or digital ASI type cameras capable of videoing the night side of the Moon at least 10 frames per sec and capable of recording starts down to magnitude 10 at these frame rates. The typical time between detectable impact flashes is a few hours but as there is a strong meteor shower on during 12-14 Dec, we would expect to capture a few impacts during this time.

Authors: Detlef Koschny, TUM, Tony Cook, U. of Aberystwyth, Lisa Maria Alessi, IMATI-CNR. Abstract text Copyright © 2025 IMATI-MI, Laboratorio Sistemi Informativi Multimediali.

ORION Last Month – 15 Oct 2025

October 15, 2025 ORION Meeting

- Welcome and introductions
- Announcements
 - Successful September 29 and October 2 TAO stargazes
 - October 18 Stargaze at Tamke-Allan (new moon)
 - Check out the ORION exhibit at the Oak Ridge Public Library
 - Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO) activities
- Presentation:
 - **Joshua Gray** "Astronomy at the Obed WSR"
 - Ted Barnes - Occultation update
 - Astrophotography
- Close

ORION President Don Spong opens the 15 Oct 2025 ORION Monthly Meeting.

ORION Last Month (cont.)

Astronomy at Obed Wild and Scenic River - Joshua Gray

Our speaker for the ORION Presentation of 15 Oct 2025 was park ranger Joshua Gray, who told us about the many impressive and well-attended astronomy outreach activities provided by the staff at the Obed Wild and Scenic River, through the National Park Service and the TWRA (Catoosa Wildlife Management Area). The Obed WSR, established in 1976, comprises 3500 acres of federal property, and an additional 1723 acres of state and private property. Their mission is to preserve and protect this area, and provide nature related programs for interested visitors. Joshua discussed the work and duties of his associates, and encouraged ORION astronomers to visit Obed and image the skies there ourselves.

Joshua receiving his ORION speaker's cup from Don Spong and David Fields.

ORION Last Month (cont.)

Joshua shares the skies at Obed.

ORION Last Month (cont.)

Don is awarded his Dark Star for observing the occultation by 1298 Nocturna on 02 Oct 2025.

DARK STAR AWARD

*Occultation of star TYC 6859-00173-1 by 1298 Nocturna
Observed at TAO, 08:33:38 pm Eastern 02 Oct 2025
Awardee: D. Spong*

Events and Calendars, Sky Maps and Occultations

Star, Moon, Comet and Meteorgazing at TAO in 2025

We enthusiastically invite visitors to attend our Public Stargaze events, held at our dark-sky site, the Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO) near Kingston, Tennessee. These events are intended especially for visitors, so our buildings and facilities will be open, and there will be astronomy talks as well as public skywatching.

In Jan-Jun 2025 we plan to hold fixed-calendar public Stargaze events on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These weekend events are especially appropriate for families. We also hold public special events, such as a “Full Moonrise,” with associated Moon Music, and the occasional comet watch. The annual Perseid Meteor watch in mid-August is especially popular.

The precise dates of many of these events depend on the local weather conditions, and cannot be specified *definitively* long in advance. As an approximate guide, see the TAOCalendar pages following. Once a date is finalized we usually confirm it through the ORION online message site ORION astronomy@groups.io. Likely and unlikely dates for TAO events may be inferred from the weather predictions at TAO by Clear Sky Charts (cleardarksky dot com) and Astrospheric (astrospheric dot com).

Please confirm event dates before proceeding to TAO.

In view of the rather challenging approach road to TAO, “Observatory Way,” first-time visitors should plan to arrive before dark. Driving instructions are given at: <https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/visit.htm>

Some instructions follow, since people may be unfamiliar with procedures for stargazing at a dark-sky site.

ORION members are invited to arrive early with their telescopes and mounts, to prepare for evening observing and to share refreshments. Please bring a red flashlight, or a headband with a red-light option.

Visitors who wish to acquire red lights or red-light headbands for observing may find them at many commercial amateur astronomy sites, such as [https:// www dot high pointscientific dot com](https://www.highpointscientific.com). The “Lepro LE” LED Headlamp, model 3200008, available from Amazon for about \$10 (Aug. 2024) is a personal favorite. This is rechargeable and has separate red and white led buttons, with several brightness settings. A caution: For amateur astronomy, brighter lights are NOT preferred, and WHITE lights are highly discouraged. Please use only red lights while the Stargaze is in progress.

Parking is available on site; on entering TAO **stay to the right**, and *please use the parking area below and right (Southwest) of the TAO buildings and observing area, near the treeline*. And **PLEASE NO HEADLIGHTS ON SITE.**

Visitors are encouraged to interact with ORION astronomers who have set up and may be operating telescopes and other astronomical equipment. We enjoy public discussions, and regard this sharing of information as a primary goal of our organization. Visitors are welcome to coffee and other refreshments.

TAO Public Stargazing: A Note Regarding Scheduling and Access in 2025

In 2025 we are reverting to an earlier schedule of having our Public Stargaze nights on every first and third Saturday. Of course this assumes good weather; if the weather is not suitable, a changed schedule will be announced on the group site [ORIONastronomy @ groups.io](https://groups.io/g/ORIONastronomy).

We decided that the previous (2024) schedule of a once-monthly Public Stargaze was insufficient, and having a Moon visible in some phase other than close to New gives our visitors an obvious and interesting object for viewing.

During Daylight Savings Time (mid-March through early November) we plan to hold our Public Stargaze events over the hours of approximately 8:00 pm - 11:00 pm, with some nominal variation.

If it is already dark when you arrive, please dim your headlights on the TAO grounds, follow the right branch of the access road, and park to the right of the TAO building, near the treeline.

Note: Parking in or near the elevated flat observing area at the front (East) of the TAO building is reserved for astronomers who are bringing their equipment.

Additional information for visitors may be found on the previous page and following two pages of this issue.

TAO Public Stargazes in November: Sats 01 & 15 Nov 2025

Sat 01 Nov 2025

Sunset	6:43 pm
Civ dusk	7:10 pm
Ast dusk	8:10 pm
Moonrise	4:23 pm
Moonset*	3:31 am
	*02 Nov

Moon illum. 79%

**Waxing Gibbous Moon.
Bright Moon during this event.**

Sat 15 Nov 2025

Sunset	6:32 pm
Civ dusk	6:59 pm
Ast dusk	8:01 pm
Moonrise	3:56 am
Moonset	4:04 pm

Moon illum. 19%

**Waning Crescent Moon.
No Moon visible during this event.**

TAO Public Stargazes in December: Sat 06 & 20 Dec 2025

Sat 06 Dec 2025

Sunset	6:25 pm
Civ dusk	6:54 pm
Ast dusk	7:57 pm
Moonrise	8:10 pm
Moonset*	11:35 am
	*07 Dec

Moon illum. 96%

**Waning Gibbous Moon.
Bright Moon during this event.**

Sat 20 Dec 2025

Sunset	6:26 pm
Civ dusk	6:55 pm
Ast dusk	7:58 pm
Moonrise	9:31 am
Moonset	6:52 pm

Moon illum. 0%

**Waxing Crescent Moon.
No Moon visible during this event.**

TAO Calendars

Jan-Jun & Jul-Dec 2025; Nov & Dec 2025

The principle public events for visitors at TAO are the **Public Stargazes**, held at TAO during 2025 on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These are listed in the “**Public Fixed Events**” **TAO Calendar** for six month periods, currently Jul-Dec 2025. These appear on the two pages immediately following.

Additional notable events will be included in monthly “**Special Events**” **TAO Calendars**. These include public events that do not have a fixed date long in advance, such as the **International Friendship Stargaze** in Oak Ridge, and special TAO events such as **Asteroid Occultations, Meteor Showers, Full Moonrises, Lunar (and other) Eclipses, Comet Watches**, and perhaps the occasional musical event.

These “Special Events” calendars for the current and subsequent months appear after the two six-month “Public Stargaze” calendars.

The facilities in the TAO buildings onsite will be open to the public during the “Public Fixed Events,” and will also usually be available when TAO is open to the public for some of the “Special Events.” **Please inquire regarding whether TAO will be open to the public for any “Special Event” you may wish to attend, since some may be restricted.** We will of course always try to accommodate enthusiastic visitors.

We recommend checking a TAO website such as <http://www.roanestate.edu/obs> before visiting, to confirm that listed events will proceed as planned; weather conditions for example may require a cancellation or change of date.

TAO Calendar Public Stargaze

Jan-Jun 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 04 Jan 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 18 Jan 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Feb 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Feb 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Mar 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Mar 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 05 Apr 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 19 Apr 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 03 May 2025	<small>canceled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 17 May 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 07 Jun 2025	<small>cancelled</small> ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 21 Jun 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm

These 2025 TAO Public Stargaze events are scheduled for fixed calendar days during the weekend, which will hopefully prove convenient for many visitors with families, especially those bringing younger astronomers. Cancellations often take place in Winter and Spring, due to cold or icy conditions, or overcast and rainy skies.

TAOCalendar Public Stargaze

Jul-Dec 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 05 Jul 2025	^{cancelled} ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 19 Jul 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 02 Aug 2025	^{cancelled} ★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 16 Aug 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sun 07 Sep 2025	^{moved} ★	"1 st Sat" Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 20 Sep 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 04 Oct 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:30 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 18 Oct 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:30 pm	10:00 pm
Mon 03 Nov 2025	^{moved} ★	"1 st Sat" Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Nov 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 06 Dec 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	6:30 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 20 Dec 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	6:30 pm	10:00 pm

These 2025 TAO Public Stargaze events are scheduled for fixed calendar days during the weekend, which will hopefully prove convenient for many visitors with families, especially those bringing younger astronomers. Cancellations often take place in Winter, due to cold or icy conditions, or overcast and rainy skies.

TAOCalendar Special Events (all times Eastern)

Nov 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 01 Nov 2025		1 st Sat Public Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sun 02 Nov 2025		End of DST 2025		1:00 am
Wed 05 Nov 2025		Full Moon 08:19 am Eastern		
Sat 15 Nov 2025		3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Thu 20 Nov 2025		New Moon 01:47 am Eastern		

TAOCalendar Special Events (all times Eastern)

Dec 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Thu 04 Dec 2025		Full Moon 06:14 pm Eastern		
Sat 06 Dec 2025		1 st Sat Public Stargaze	6:30 pm	10:00 pm
Ddd nn Dec 2025		Festival of the Winter Solstice	6:00 pm	t.b.a.
Fri-Mon 12-15 Dec 2025		Lunar Impact Flash (LIF) Campaign	00:49 am 12 Dec 2025	06:09 am 15 Dec 2025
Fri 19 Dec 2025		New Moon 08:43 pm Eastern		

Public Stargaze of Sat 18 Oct 2025

- Ted Barnes

Sat 18 Oct 2025

Sunset	6:59 pm
Civ dusk	7:25 pm
Ast dusk	8:25 pm
Moonrise	5:03 am
Moonset	5:37 pm

Moon illum. 8%

Waning Crescent Moon.

No Moon was visible during this event.

The word was that TAO would be open for this event by 7 pm, which sounded promising to those who liked to arrive early to set up their equipment. However there was also a suggestion from David that we arrive by 7:15 pm to discuss our plans for the evening, since a large number of scouts would likely arrive. I had updated an asteroid talk in the afternoon, so I felt ready to entertain an enthusiastic group of youngish visitors. Surely all adolescents like asteroids. However it developed that the scouts had apparently postponed their visit, since the weather was overcast. Another group however did plan to appear, this being a group of homeschooled kiddies. OK that sounds fine, too. All kids like telescopes, right? However the numbers were not quite as expected. First quite a few arrived with their parents, and came into the classroom and found places to sit. We don't exactly have an excess of chairs, but we did our best to accommodate them.

Public Stargaze of Sat 18 Oct 2025 (cont.)

Initially we appeared to be doing ok, and David began a welcome address, which evolved into a talk about Sky Rulers. This was regularly interrupted as more and more kiddies arrived, seemingly doubling and even tripling the initial numbers. I was concerned about their comfort, as the room was now basically standing room only.

Normally one might expect an overflow crowd to populate the outside for views of the sky, but the sky was unfortunately overcast, so everyone appeared happy to stay inside for the lectures.

I had prepared a talk about the asteroid occultation we had observed at TAO, and people seemed happy to hear about asteroids. I assumed that the kiddies associated them with dinosaurs. In any case our large audience (of perhaps 25) seemed quite happy.

Our SRO audience lining the wall.

Public Stargaze of Sat 18 Oct 2025 (cont.)

Initially we appeared to be doing ok, and David began a welcome address, which evolved into a talk about Sky Rulers. This was regularly interrupted as more and more kiddies arrived, seemingly doubling and even tripling the initial numbers. I was concerned about their comfort, as the room was now basically standing room only.

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Our SRO audience lining the wall.

Public Stargaze of Sat 18 Oct 2025 (cont.)

After by talk Don Spong gave a presentation showing a wide range of beautiful astronomical images, mainly from his images captured at TAO. This talk, ranging from solar system objects to stars, star clusters, nebulae and external galaxies, was very popular. During the ORION Monthly meeting on Wed 15 Oct we had presented Don with a Dark Star Award for recording his first occultation, and I was pleased to see that he was wearing the award for his talk.

Don leads the audience on a tour of the universe through astrophotography.
9:06 pm, 25 Oct 2025.

Public Stargaze of Sat 18 Oct 2025 (cont.)

David returned and announced that promising views of Saturn were available, so after his talk most of the audience exited, to see what was on offer outside. Rob had set up a view of Saturn for any interested parties, and drew a crowd of viewers wanting to see Saturn through the Meade. Our visitors were also interested to see images of the Veil Nebula that Don was producing, which could be seen on his tablet.

Although I hadn't brought my telescope, I discovered that my green hand laser, which I had fetched to show people the stars that were occasionally visible through the clouds, was extremely interesting to the kiddies. I was surrounded by an enthusiastic group asking to have their turn at pointing things out in the sky. I realized that this age group, perhaps 5 to 10, could easily be entertained by seeing the green laser beam reaching into the sky. The fact that only a few stars were visible (I recall seeing Cassiopeia for awhile) was not really a hindrance for this large, happy group.

Rob giving a last few visitors a view of Saturn.
10:00 pm, 25 Oct 2025.

The Chimaera Campaign. Mon/Tue 20/21 Oct 2025 - Ted Barnes

I first noticed mention of the occultation by 623 Chimaera in the [IOTAOccultations] discussion postings by the UVa occultations group in early Oct. They were promoting a campaign of observations of a 21 Oct 2025 occultation by this asteroid, motivated by a planned MBR Explorer spacecraft flyby of 623 Chimaera in the 2030s. Previously only a single occultation involving this asteroid had been reported. UVa anticipated having a sizeable campaign with ~8 telescopes; eventually something like 19 different observing sites joined this effort (many were UVa remotes). I mentioned the occultation in discussions with a few other possibly interested ORION members, and asked David if TAO might be opened for this effort, since TAO was within the shadow path. The obvious complication was the early hour; the occultation midpoint at TAO was predicted to be 3:16:42 am Eastern. I was hesitant to encourage my colleagues to participate in an observation in view of the stressful overnight effort this would entail. However I thought I SHOULD mention it, since the IOTA community evidently considered this to be an important effort, and many people would be involved in the campaign. And my previous accidental joining of a campaign to observe 253 Mathilda on 28 Apr 2024 was still a pleasant memory. In any case I thought some people might enjoy a Dark Stargaze on a clear moonless night with a prediction of excellent weather, independent of this very late occultation.

Mon 20 Oct 2025

Sunset	6:57 pm
Civ dusk	7:23 pm
Ast dusk	8:22 pm
Moonrise	7:00 am
Moonset	6:23 pm

Moon illum. 1%

Waning Crescent Moon.
No Moon visible during this event.

Beginning a careful, unhurried alignment of the 8" ORION Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph with CPWI at the TAO Northeast pad. 8:13 pm Eastern, 20 Oct 2025

The Chimaera Campaign. (cont.)

Prospects for observing this event appeared to improve when David stated that Noah would be having his class at TAO that evening, and would be willing to open at 6pm to accommodate any interested astronomers. Unfortunately Art Allison had a musical conflict, and Richard Piety would be on holiday. To my surprise, Rob Fowler did agree to participate in the full very late night event, and we arranged to arrive at TAO around 7pm. I had assumed that he would be uninterested in an effectively overnight occultation event, but I had apparently been wrong. I went ahead with making observing plans, drawing star charts, and packing my van.

On arrival at TAO I met Rob, who had been uncertain of the event's status, and whether I would appear. Apparently a student had earlier reported that a fallen log had blocked the access road, and Noah had accordingly cancelled his class. Afterwards two female students had removed the obstruction, which was not so impressive after all. The upshot was that although there would be no astronomy class at TAO that evening, Rob and I were nonetheless there by 7pm to set up for the late night occultation. Rob also wanted to do some work on the Meade; he was looking into off-axis guiding, and I had a suitable spare ZWO camera (model ASI432MM), and was interesting in trying to help with that effort.

So, soon after 7pm I began assembling my observing setup, for once at a leisurely pace, since eight hours remained until the 3:16 am occultation by 623 Chimaera.

Sagittarius and star-clouds setting over the Meade glow-dome.
8:14 pm Eastern, 20 Oct 2025

The Chimaera Campaign. (cont.)

The orbit of asteroid 623 Chimaera, from JPL's Horizons program. This shows the inner solar system at 3:00 am Eastern, 21 Oct 2025, just before the occultation.

The Chimaera Campaign. (cont.)

Path of the shadow of asteroid 623 Chimaera through the local region during the 3:16 am Eastern occultation of 21 Oct 2025. Image from Occult Watcher. The center of the path is a green line, with the expected shadow edges in red. The TAO site is indicated, and the parallel faint grey chords show the transverse locations of other observers on the asteroid's profile.

The Chimaera Campaign. (cont.)

Position of asteroid 623 Chimaera in Andromeda at the time of the occultation.
3:16:42 am Eastern, 21 Oct 2025. Image from TheSkyX.

The Chimaera Campaign. (cont.)

There is an interesting phenomenon at TAO, which is that sporadic visitors will arrive hoping to participate in astronomy even when there has been no announcement of a public event, especially on notably clear, dark nights. This evening we had five visitors, despite there being no official announcement of TAO being open! The first visitor, James McCarthy, was looking for a site where it might be possible to view the two comets (Lemmon and Swan) which had been in the news of late. These are early evening objects which are currently just at naked-eye magnitudes, so we could at least tell him where they might be found. He was quite knowledgeable about astronomy and we encouraged him to visit TAO in future, but he had just sold his residence and was moving to Idaho in the very near future, so that was that. Next to appear was a young couple who were interested in seeing the Orion meteors, and were happy to remain in their car, and accidentally turned on their lights surprisingly often. Rob then volunteered to drive to civilization and return with some drinks and snacks; coffee especially appealed to me. While Rob was gone another car appeared with two women and two dogs, who also left their lights on initially, and called to me (Ted) by name. I assumed I knew them from some past astronomy event, but they had actually just encountered Rob on our access road, who encouraged them to visit TAO. They were on a major driving holiday from New York City (!), and were looking for a location where they might view the night sky. As it developed they were very enthusiastic about astronomy, and had many questions for us. When Rob returned he used the Meade to show them views of Saturn, the Orion Nebula and other sights, and they enjoyed discussing Jersey. I showed them my observing setup, and explained tonight's asteroid occultation. Their little dogs remained unfriendly throughout.

While Rob had been out looking for supplies I had recalibrated my own PHD2 guiding program (which I think actually made it worse; it had been running very well earlier in the evening). I had earlier finished my CPWI alignment by accepting the program's offer to run ASPA (the All Star Polar Alignment routine), which I normally decline, to save time and effort. According to the CPWI program's numbers, ASPA vastly improved my polar alignment, so the PHD2 guiding corrections now appeared much less significant. I was well rewarded by my careful, leisurely alignment on 10 stars "from scratch" earlier that evening, these being Alioth, Mirfak, Caph, Mirach, Edasich, Eltanin, Vega, Albireo, Rasalhague and Nunki, after I had initially aligned the mount's platform on Polaris.

We also worked on off-axis guiding on the Meade, and tried to get it to work using PHD2, but I had no experience with this technique, so we mainly learned that the obvious PHD2 parameter guesses didn't appear to work. Rob will likely benefit from future online background reading regarding how to implement this technique on the Meade.

The Chimaera Campaign. (cont.)

With the departure of our visitors around midnight we settled in for the long wait until 3:16 am and the occultation, Rob experimenting with Meade control, and me doing “station keeping” at my 8” ORION Ritchey-Chrétien Astrograph. As the event would take place high in the West, near Alt@Azi = $63^\circ @ 278^\circ$, one might think that one could find a bright star near the faint target star and simply let the system guide on that bright star through the evening. As the target star was close to Mirach (β And), it might seem the obvious choice. However this was not feasible, as is clear from the Alt-Azi position of the target star through the night:

<u>Time Eastern</u>	<u>target star position (Alt@Azi)</u>
09:00 pm 20 Oct	$42^\circ @ 72^\circ$
10:00 pm	$53^\circ @ 77^\circ$
11:00 pm	$65^\circ @ 82^\circ$
midnight 21 Oct	$78^\circ @ 88^\circ$
01:00 am	$89^\circ @ 165^\circ$
02:00 am	$78^\circ @ 272^\circ$
03:00 am	$66^\circ @ 278^\circ$
event: 03:16:42 am	$62.4^\circ @ 279.0^\circ$
04:00 am	$54^\circ @ 283^\circ$

Ouch! Since the target star would evidently pass very close to the zenith, reaching a maximum Alt of 89.45° just before 1:01 am, trying to guide on the event region through the night clearly invited a disaster, with a coordinate singularity and a possible mount-OTA collision.

I instead decided on the less dramatic procedure of slewing to a position of roughly Alt@Azi = $40^\circ @ 275^\circ$, where I would hop between bright stars, waiting for the occultation region to approach. Accordingly I hopped between Markab and Scheat, and then the higher-Alt pair Algenib and Alpheratz, as the night passed.

Around 1am a new complication arose. Dew! Who could have anticipated dew late on a cold October night? What an oversight! Soon my work table and keyboards were damp, and it grew worse as the early morning hours progressed. My computer monitors misted over, and I had to remove their red plastic sheets. I used most of a role of paper towels I had fortunately brought in trying to keep the work areas, the OTA and its light shield dry. As we passed 2:30 am they were all very damp. Guiding was now failing after a few

The Chimaera Campaign. (cont.)

seconds, and I found condensation covering the guidescope's front lens. I dried it as best I could and put the lens cap back on the guidescope, hoping to save a guiding capability for the event itself if needed. I was now quite worried about condensation on the OTA's primary mirror, especially when the OTA would be elevated to the higher Alt where the event would occur. Occasionally we were helped by a light breeze, but the condensation seemed to return, "wetter" with each encounter. This was becoming a disaster.

As we entered the final 30 minutes before 3:16 am I simply had to ignore these problems and proceed approximately as planned. I slewed the OTA out of the safer, dryer lower Altitudes, up to "δ And" at 2:45 am, and then still higher to Mirach at 3:00 am. At least SharpCap's plate solve and resync function had been working on most attempts; this was valuable in confirming my location. I then did a "Go To (RA, Dec)" slew to the target area, and at 3:08 am noted that I could see the tiny close pair of target star and asteroid in the field. (They were of very similar brightness, according to Occult Watcher having magnitudes of 13.8 for the asteroid, and 13.9 for the target star.) The field stars matched my little sketch map, *albeit* inverted as usual. I just had to survive the next few minutes.

Looking back to the East before the event, one can see Orion, Sirius and Procyon at right, and at upper left Gemini, featuring a bright Jupiter. 2:36 am Eastern, 21 Oct 2025

The Chimaera Campaign. (cont.)

Next yet another potential disaster arose. Rob yelled at me from the glow-dome where he pointed his laser into the sky, illuminating a low layer of fog overhead drifting up from Watts Bar Lake. Great. I think I replied “I don’t wish to know that.” since I already had enough problems. But there were admittedly already hints of fog in the air. Just a few minutes to go ... Rob came over to watch developments. After I pointed out the nice star-and-asteroid close pair still visible on my damp display screen, at 3:15:00 am as planned I hit the Start Capture button on SharpCap. I had set SharpCap to record a 400-frame SER movie of longish 500ms@Gain480 frames, with the maximum camera gain chosen to aid in recording these two faint 14th magnitude objects. This would record the period 3:15:00 - 3:18:20 am, with the predicted occultation midpoint of 3:16:42 am hopefully being close to the middle of the SER movie file. Perhaps unnecessarily (and recklessly?) I captured 1920x1200 full frames, each about 2.3 MB. Also, a few days earlier I had attached an 0.75x photoreducer to the QHY174MGPS camera, so I was recording a field about 31’ x 19’ in extent, somewhat larger than usual.

About 5 minutes before the occultation the asteroid and star could no longer be separated visually, and we watched this combined image on the screen as SharpCap was capturing the frames. The question was, would we see any dimming during the occultation as the asteroid eclipsed the target star, and the combined 13.1-magnitude source dimmed to a single 13.8-magnitude asteroid? We watched the image carefully as the predicted occultation time approached. Then it arrived, and you could easily see the pointlike object drop considerably in brightness. It remained dimmed for about 2 seconds, and then came back to full brightness. We had seen a 13.9-magnitude star being occulted “live” on the screen!

We were now very happy and enthusiastic people. Despite the many complications we had seen the event, and once SharpCap finished its task, we had recorded it as well!

The Chimaera Campaign. (cont.)

Success!

A lightcurve plot from the SER image file, generated by Pymovie, showing the brightness of the target star UCAC4 626-004193 (blue), a brighter comparison star (green), and an empty field region (red). The occultation takes place near the middle of the plot, as planned. On 25 Oct my UVa colleagues used the PyOTE fitting program to find a solution with the highest SNR, with disappearance and reappearance times [Eastern] and a duration (with 1σ error bars) of $D = 03:16:40.21(6)$, $R = 03:16:42.13(6)$, and $dur = 1.92(2)$ secs. The disappearance time was about 1 to 2 seconds earlier than predicted, depending on the reference.

The Chimaera Campaign. (cont.)

This is a single 4sG400 exposure centered on 3:22:58 am Eastern, 21 Oct 2025, 6m17s after the occultation. The pair is g-mag 13.9 target star UCAC4 626-004193 (L) and mag 13.8 asteroid 623 Chimaera (R), at a separation of ~ 4 px, consistent with the expected separation of about $4.0''$ at the time of this image. The bright star is the type G5 g-mag 7.8 star SAO 54610, at a distance of $2'10''$ from Chimaera. In this image N is up and E is left.

The Chimaera Campaign. (cont.)

Of course the evening didn't end with the successful observation and imaging of the occultation. Afterwards there was the requisite period of sitting around admiring the sky, and feeling good about everything. For future reference, fog from Watts Bar Lake doesn't necessarily dissipate immediately after the astrophotography ends. In this case it continued to thicken as we packed our equipment, and by about 4pm only a few bright stars were still visible through the fog. Hand lasers could be used to identify fog layers, see image below. We had been very lucky with the timing of the occultation.

A fog layer at TAO illuminated by a hand laser.
3:30 am Eastern, 21 Oct 2025

The Chimaera Campaign. (cont.)

The final results of this campaign will depend on an analysis by the UVa group, once they have results from all the participating observers. As of 23 Oct 2025, 7 of the 19 stations listed by Occult Watcher as participants had reported their preliminary observed occultation durations, ranging from 3.5 secs near the midline to 1.7 secs at 21.9 km from the midline. Our result from TAO of about 1.9 secs at 18.0 km from the midline appears roughly consistent with the other results reported to date.

Once the results of the individual sites and their associated occultation timing datasets have been reviewed by the collaboration in a careful reanalysis, they plan to release accurate results for the extent of 623 Chimaera, together with an approximate profile of the asteroid. The expectation is that these results will be published in several months. This will undoubtedly be a great improvement over the previous estimate of a diameter of *ca.* 44 km, apparently from one observation of an earlier occultation.

The most amusing of the observers' brief comments reported in Occult Watcher to date is that of David Durham, from a station at -8.4 km from midline. He reports:

“No observation – Chased off site by Indian Reservation police.”

Private Public Stargaze of Mon 03 Nov 2025

- Ted Barnes

Several rainy days in late October resulted in the delay of the nominal Public Stargaze on Sat 01 Nov 2025 until the following Monday, 03 Nov 2025. The transition to standard time is often unsettling, and in this case led to a surprisingly dark sky as early as 6:30 pm. The nominal event start time of 7:00 pm seems unnecessarily late, and should perhaps be moved to 6:30 pm for Public Stargazes in November, after the transition to Standard Time. Since we had several ORION people out with illness or schedule conflicts, and the very bright moon was discouraging, we only had three astronomers present, Don Spong, Rob Fowler, and eventually Ted Barnes (moi), who was delayed by a late-arriving crew of house maintenance workers.

Mon 03 Nov 2025

Sunset	5:41 pm
Civ dusk	6:08 pm
Ast dusk	7:09 pm
Moonrise	4:20 pm
Moonset*	5:56 am
	*04 Nov

Moon illum. 94%

Waxing Gibbous Moon.
Nearly Full Moon during this event.

The view to the West, 7:01 pm Eastern, Mon 03 Nov 2025.
The location of C/2025 A6 Lemmon is indicated.

Private Public Stargaze of Mon 03 Nov 2025 (cont.)

Don Spong indicating the position of Comet C/2025 A6 Lemmon in Ophiuchus. 7:01 pm Eastern, Mon 03 Nov 2025. For Don's comet images, see the Astrophotography section.

Private Public Stargaze of Mon 03 Nov 2025 (cont.)

Don was drawn by the opportunity to capture images of two early evening comets in the West. The public media had promoted these comets extensively in recent weeks, and as of this date they were just barely naked-eye objects; Comet C/2025 A6 Lemmon was in the constellation Ophiuchus, near magnitude 4.8, and C/2025 R2 Swan was near the water-jug asterism in Aquarius, at about 6th magnitude. When I arrived Don and Rob had moved their vehicles to near the North TAO exit, near the one TAO tree, and Don had already captured an impressive image of Comet Lemmon. (See the Astrophotography section.) Accordingly I set up my camp chair nearby, between the two vehicles, and scanned the sky low to the West with my binoculars. Despite the intense moonlight coming from behind us, I eventually found a faintish star with nebulosity, which I decided could only be Comet Lemmon. Alas my SkyMaster binoculars had an alignment problem, so I saw everything doubled unless I used it as a monocular.

The very intense moonlight to the East. To the Moon's left are α and β Arietis, at upper left is Almach (γ 1 And), and Saturn is at upper right. 7:44 pm Eastern, 03 Nov 2025.

Private Public Stargaze of Mon 03 Nov 2025 (cont.)

During one search for the comet, I leaned too far to the right in my chair, which was already on a steep slope, and crashed hard into the lawn. My cell phone flew away at a high velocity and impacted Rob's van, fortunately without visible damage. We did have a long break in the classroom to shake off the dampness and moisture, and I managed to get the "atomic" clock working, in the correct time zone! Finally we decided the show was over, there were no visitors (probably there had been no announcement of having the Public Stargaze at a later date), and so we departed early, around 10 pm Eastern. Was it worth it? Well, yes, of course. Finally seeing a new comet can be used to justify almost anything.

The view to the Northeast; Perseus, with Capella rising, and the Pleiades visible at lower right, 7:51 pm Eastern, 03 Nov 2025.

The evening Sky Map for November 2025 from skymaps.com.

About the Celestial Objects

Listed on this page are several of the brighter, more interesting celestial objects visible in the evening sky this month (refer to the monthly sky map). The objects are grouped into three categories. Those that can be easily seen with the naked eye (that is, without optical aid), those easily seen with binoculars, and those requiring a telescope to be appreciated. **Note, all of the objects (except single stars) will appear more impressive when viewed through a telescope or very large binoculars.** They are grouped in this way to highlight objects that can be seen using the optical equipment that may be available to the star gazer.

Tips for Observing the Night Sky

When observing the night sky, and in particular deep-sky objects such as star clusters, nebulae, and galaxies, it's always best to observe from a dark location. Avoid direct light from street lights and other sources. If possible observe from a dark location away from the light pollution that surrounds many of today's large cities.

You will see more stars after your eyes adapt to the darkness—usually about 10 to 20 minutes after you go outside. Also, if you need to use a torch to view the sky map, cover the light bulb with red cellophane. This will preserve your dark vision.

Finally, even though the Moon is one of the most stunning objects to view through a telescope, its light is so bright that it brightens the sky and makes many of the fainter objects very difficult to see. So try to observe the evening sky on moonless nights around either New Moon or Last Quarter.

Astronomical Glossary

Conjunction – An alignment of two celestial bodies such that they present the least angular separation as viewed from Earth.

Constellation – A defined area of the sky containing a star pattern.

Diffuse Nebula – A cloud of gas illuminated by nearby stars.

Double Star – Two stars that appear close to each other in the sky; either linked by gravity so that they orbit each other (binary star) or lying at different distances from Earth (optical double). Apparent separation of stars is given in seconds of arc (").

Ecliptic – The path of the Sun's center on the celestial sphere as seen from Earth.

Elongation – The angular separation of two celestial bodies. For Mercury and Venus the greatest elongation occurs when they are at their most angular distance from the Sun as viewed from Earth.

Galaxy – A mass of up to several billion stars held together by gravity.

Globular Star Cluster – A ball-shaped group of several thousand old stars.

Light Year (ly) – The distance a beam of light travels at 300,000 km/sec in one year.

Magnitude – The brightness of a celestial object as it appears in the sky.

Open Star Cluster – A group of tens or hundreds of relatively young stars.

Opposition – When a celestial body is opposite the Sun in the sky.

Planetary Nebula – The remnants of a shell of gas blown off by a star.

Universal Time (UT) – A time system used by astronomers. Also known as Greenwich Mean Time. USA Eastern Standard Time (for example, New York) is 5 hours behind UT.

Variable Star – A star that changes brightness over a period of time.

NORTHERN HEMISPHERE
NOVEMBER 2025

CELESTIAL OBJECTS

Sky maps
com

Easily Seen with the Naked Eye

Altair	Aql	• Brightest star in Aquila. Name means "the flying eagle". Dist=16.7 ly.
Capella	Aur	• The 6th brightest star. Appears yellowish in color. Spectroscopic binary. Dist=42 ly.
δ Cephei	Cep	• Cepheid prototype. Mag varies between 3.5 & 4.4 over 5.366 days. Mag 6 companion.
Deneb	Cyg	• Brightest star in Cygnus. One of the greatest known supergiants. Dist=1,400±200 ly.
α Herculis	Her	• Semi-regular variable. Magnitude varies between 3.1 & 3.9 over 90 days. Mag 5.4 companion.
Vega	Lyr	• The 5th brightest star in the sky. A blue-white star. Dist=25.0 ly.
Algol	Per	• Famous eclipsing binary star. Magnitude varies between 2.1 & 3.4 over 2.867 days.
Fomalhaut	PsA	• Brightest star in Piscis Austrinus. In Arabic the "fish's mouth". Dist=25 ly.
Pleiades	Tau	• The Seven Sisters. Spectacular cluster. Many more stars visible in binoculars. Dist=399 ly.
Hyades	Tau	• Large V-shaped star cluster. Binoculars reveal many more stars. Dist=152 ly.
Aldebaran	Tau	• Brightest star in Taurus. It is not associated with the Hyades star cluster. Dist=66.7 ly.
Polaris	UMi	• The North Pole Star. A telescope reveals an unrelated mag 8 companion star. Dist=433 ly.

Easily Seen with Binoculars

M31	And	• The Andromeda Galaxy. Most distant object visible to naked eye. Dist=2.5 million ly.
M2	Aqr	• Resembles a fuzzy star in binoculars.
η Aquilae	Aql	• Bright Cepheid variable. Mag varies between 3.6 & 4.5 over 7.166 days. Dist=1,200 ly.
M38	Aur	• Stars appear arranged in "π" or cross shape. Dist=4,300 ly.
M36	Aur	• About half size of M38. Located in rich Milky Way star field. Dist=4,100 ly.
M37	Aur	• Very fine star cluster. Discovered by Messier in 1764. Dist=4,400 ly.
υ Cephei	Cep	• Herschel's Garnet Star. One of the reddest stars. Mag 3.4 to 5.1 over 730 days.
Mira	Cet	• Famous long period variable star. Mag varies between 3.0 & 10.1 over 332 days.
χ Cygni	Cyg	• Long period pulsating red giant. Magnitude varies between 3.3 & 14.2 over 407 days.
M39	Cyg	• May be visible to the naked eye under good conditions. Dist=900 ly.
ν Draconis	Dra	• Wide pair of white stars. One of the finest binocular pairs in the sky. Dist=100 ly.
M13	Her	• Best globular in northern skies. Discovered by Halley in 1714. Dist=23,000 ly.
M92	Her	• Fainter and smaller than M13. Use a telescope to resolve its stars.
ε Lyrae	Lyr	• Famous Double Double. Binoculars show a double star. High power reveals each a double.
R Lyrae	Lyr	• Semi-regular variable. Magnitude varies between 3.9 & 5.0 over 46.0 days.
IC 4665	Oph	• Large, scattered open cluster. Visible with binoculars.
6633	Oph	• Scattered open cluster. Visible with binoculars.
M15	Peg	• Only globular known to contain a planetary nebula (Mag 14, d=1"). Dist=30,000 ly.
Double Cluster	Per	• Double Cluster in Perseus. NGC 869 & 884. Excellent in binoculars. Dist=7,300 ly.
M25	Sgr	• Bright cluster located about 6 deg N of "teapot's" lid. Dist=1,900 ly.
253	Ucl	• Fine, large, cigar-shaped galaxy. Requires dark sky. Member of Sculptor Group.
Mizar & Alcor	UMa	• Good eyesight or binoculars reveals 2 stars. Not a binary. Mizar has a mag 4 companion.
Cr 399	Vul	• Coathanger asterism or "Brocchi's Cluster". Not a true star cluster. Dist=218 to 1,140 ly.

Telescopic Objects

γ Andromedae	And	• Attractive double star. Bright orange star with mag 5 blue companion. Sep=9.8".
7009	Aqr	• Saturn Nebula. Requires 8-inch telescope to see Saturn-like appendages.
7293	Aqr	• Helix Nebula. Spans nearly 1/4 deg. Requires dark sky. Dist=300 ly.
γ Arietis	Ari	• Impressive looking double blue-white star. Visible in a small telescope. Sep=7.8".
η Cassiopeiae	Cas	• Yellow star mag 3.4 & orange star mag 7.5. Dist=19 ly. Orbit=480 years. Sep=12".
Albireo	Cyg	• Beautiful double star. Contrasting colours of orange and blue-green. Sep=34.4".
61 Cygni	Cyg	• Attractive double star. Mags 5.2 & 6.1 orange dwarfs. Dist=11.4 ly. Sep=28.4".
γ Delphini	Del	• Appear yellow & white. Mags 4.3 & 5.2. Dist=100 ly. Struve 2725 double in same field.
β Lyrae	Lyr	• Eclipsing binary. Mag varies between 3.3 & 4.3 over 12.940 days. Fainter mag 7.2 blue star.
M57	Lyr	• Ring Nebula. Magnificent object. Smoke-ring shape. Dist=4,100 ly.
M17	Sgr	• Omega Nebula. Contains the star cluster NGC 6618. Dist=4,900 ly.
M11	Sct	• Wild Duck Cluster. Resembles a globular through binoculars. V-shaped. Dist=5,600 ly.
M16	Ser	• Eagle Nebula. Requires a telescope of large aperture. Dist=8,150 ly.
M1	Tau	• Crab Nebula. Remnant from supernova which was visible in 1054. Dist=6,500 ly.
M33	Tri	• Fine face-on spiral galaxy. Requires a large aperture telescope. Dist=2.3 million ly.
M81	UMa	• Beautiful spiral galaxy visible with binoculars. Easy to see in a telescope.
M82	UMa	• Close to M81 but much fainter and smaller.
M27	Vul	• Dumbbell Nebula. Large, twin-lobed shape. Most spectacular planetary. Dist=975 ly.

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Astrophotography

The Comets of November

- Don Spong

Many comets have been passing through the inner solar system recently. I've been fortunate to be able to get to TAO on clear nights to image two of these: C/2025 R2 Swan, imaged on October 18, and C/2025 A6 Lemmon, imaged on November 3. C/2025 A6 Lemmon was low near the horizon in the West on November 3 (dipping below the horizon around 8:30 pm), and C/2025 R2 Swan was higher, toward the South, on October 18. These images were made using my Celestron Edge HD, ZWOAM5 mount, Hyperstar attachment, ZWO533MC Pro camera, Williams optics guide scope, and ZWO220MM guide camera, all controlled by my ZWO ASI AIR. Around 100 30-second images were stacked for C/2025 A6 Lemmon, and 31 30-second images for Swan.

C/2025 R2 Swan – imaged at TAO October 18

The Comets of November (cont.)

C/2025 A6 Lemmon – imaged at TAO November 3

Milky Way from the Grand Canyon

- Don Spong

During the week October 21 to 26 I was in Arizona attending my 59th high school reunion. We had arranged as part of the trip to spend one night (October 24) at the Grand Canyon. The nighttime skies there were phenomenal, with better views of the Milky Way than I have ever seen at dark sky sites in Tennessee. Below are two images I took of the Milky Way from the South Rim, where we stayed. These were done using a Sony alpha 7-III mirrorless camera with a 12mm lens on a tripod. I took about twenty 25-second exposures and stacked them using the software Sequator. The first image is looking to the northern end of the Milky Way and the second is looking to the southern end.

Milky Way from the South rim of the Grand Canyon looking North

Milky Way from the Grand Canyon (cont.)

Milky Way from the South rim of the Grand Canyon looking South

Appendices

Astronomy

- tb

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate.
Exact numerical relationships are indicated as such.

1 ly = 1 ly (Julian) = *exactly* 9 460 730 472 580. 8 km = 63 241. 077 084 ... AU
c = speed of light = *exactly* 299 792 458 m/s = *exactly* ☺ 1 ly/yr.
1 AU = *exactly* 149 597 870. 7 km
1 parsec (pc) = 3. 261 598 ... light years (ly)
1 yr (Julian) = *exactly* 365.25 d = *exactly* 31 557 600 s
1 d = *exactly* 86 400 s

distance to α Cen A = 1.346(2) pc = 4.390(8) ly
distance to the center of the galaxy ~ 8 kpc ~ 25 kly (considerable uncertainty)

1 nm = 1 nanometer = 10^{-9} m *exactly*
 H_{α} wavelength = 656.2 nm

+ 0.5 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{1/5}$ x fainter =	1. 584 893 ... x fainter
+ 1 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{2/5}$ x fainter =	2. 511 886 ... x fainter
+ 2 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{4/5}$ x fainter =	6. 309 ... x fainter
+ 2.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^1 x fainter =	10 x fainter
+ 3 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{6/5}$ x fainter =	15. 848 ... x fainter
+ 4 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{8/5}$ x fainter =	39. 810 ... x fainter
+ 5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^2 x fainter =	100 x fainter
+ 6 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{12/5}$ x fainter =	251. 188 ... x fainter
+ 7.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^3 x fainter =	1000 x fainter
+ 8 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{16/5}$ x fainter =	1584. 893 ... x fainter
+ 10 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^4 x fainter =	10 000 x fainter
+ 20 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^8 x fainter =	100 000 000 x fainter

Brightness is proportional to $1 / \text{distance}^2$

10 x more distant = *exactly* 10^2 x fainter = + 5 change in magnitude
 10^2 x more distant = *exactly* 10^4 x fainter = + 10 change in mag
 10^3 x more distant = *exactly* 10^6 x fainter = + 15 change in mag

Absolute magnitude M_{abs} is the brightness as seen from a distance of 10 pc.
 M_{abs} (our sun) = 4.83

17th mag is about 1 optical photon / $\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}$ (Barnes's rule ☺).

Astronomy (cont.)

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate.
Exact numerical relationships are indicated as such.

R.A. = RA = Right Ascension = the angle ϕ around the celestial polar axis, usually quoted in hours, minutes, and seconds (*h m s*); analogous to longitude.

Dec = Declination = the angle θ above the celestial equator, usually quoted in degrees, minutes, and seconds ($^{\circ} \ ' \ ''$); analogous to latitude.

The RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles, together with a reference epoch such as J2000.0, specify an object's direction in the sky.

A unit length vector ("unit vector") $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ pointing towards an object in the sky ("on the celestial sphere") in terms of RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles is given by

$$\boldsymbol{\eta} = \cos(\theta) \cos(\phi) \mathbf{x} + \cos(\theta) \sin(\phi) \mathbf{y} + \sin(\theta) \mathbf{z} = C(c \mathbf{x} + s \mathbf{y}) + S \mathbf{z}$$

The arc angle Θ_{12} between any two directions in the sky $\boldsymbol{\eta}_1$ and $\boldsymbol{\eta}_2$ (or any two stars) using the dot product formula and some obvious abbreviations, satisfies

$$\cos(\Theta_{12}) = \sin(\theta_1)\sin(\theta_2) + \cos(\theta_1)\cos(\theta_2)\cos(\phi_1 - \phi_2) = S_1 S_2 + C_1 C_2 c_{1-2}$$

$$1 \text{ degree} = \pi/180 \text{ radians} = 1.745 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcmin} = \pi/10800 \text{ radians} = 2.909 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcsec} = 1 \text{ asec} = \pi/648000 \text{ radians} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ mas} = 10^{-3} \text{ asec} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 km} = 4.848 \text{ mm}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 AU} = 725.3 \text{ km}$$

$$1 \text{ asec @ 1 pc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

$$1 \text{ mas @ 1 kpc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

$$\text{Image scale [asec/px]} = 206.3 * \text{pixel size}[\mu\text{m}] / \text{focal length [mm]}$$

JD = Julian Date (Astronomer's calendar) = a simple count of days starting at noon UT on Monday 1 Jan 4713 BC. That date and time was the start of Julian Day 0. The current JD can be inferred from the value on the cover of the Trapezium.

The 80 Brightest Stars

The 80 brightest stars (c/o Wikipedia), and their distances from Earth in light years, with errors (from Gaia data, or Simbad if needed as an alternative).

1	Sirius	8.709	0.0054	41	Menkalinan	81.1	0.46
2	Canopus	309.	16.	42	Atria	390.6	7.0
3	alpha Centauri A	4.395	0.0083	43	Alhena	109.3	8.2
4	Arcturus	36.72	0.22	44	Peacock	178.8	5.1
5	Vega	25.04	0.069	45	Alsephina	80.6	0.78
6	Capella	42.81	0.26	46	Mirzam	492.7	16.4
7	Rigel	863.	78.	47	Polaris	432.6	6.3
8	Procyon	11.46	0.051	48	Alphard	180.3	1.8
9	Archenar	139.4	3.4	49	Hamal	65.8	0.33
10	Betelgeuse	498.	63.	50	Diphda	96.3	0.46
11	beta Centauri	392.	24.	51	Mizar	81.1	0.93
12	Altair	16.73	0.049	52	Nunki	227.8	4.6
13	alpha Crucis	322.	16.	53	Menkent	58.8	0.21
14	Aldebaran	66.64	1.05	54	Alpheratz	97.0	1.01
15	Antares	554.	94.	55	Mirach	197.4	6.7
16	Spica	250.	13.	56	Rasalhague	48.6	0.77
17	Pollux	33.78	0.09	57	Algieba	130.1	2.7
18	Fomalhaut	25.13	0.09	58	Kochab	130.9	0.63
19	Deneb	1410	200	59	Saiph	974.	37.
20	Mimosa	279.	23.	60	Denebola	35.9	0.21
21	Regulus	79.30	0.67	61	Algol	89.9	3.47
22	Adhara	405.	7.0	62	Tiaki	177.0	4.0
23	Castor	50.68	0.032	63	Muhlifain	130.2	1.5
24	Shaula	571.2	7.5	64	Aspidiske	765.6	18.0
25	Gacrux	88.56	0.43	65	Suhail	544.5	10.0
26	Bellatrix	252.4	10.2	66	Alphecca	77.2	1.79
27	Elnath	133.9	1.9	67	Mintaka	692.5	85.
28	Miaplacidus	113.2	0.43	68	Sadr	1830	270
29	Alnilam	1980	540	69	Eltanin	154.3	0.7
30	Regor	1120	110	70	Schedar	231.5	8.2
31	Alnair	101.0	0.66	71	Naos	1080	40
32	Alnitak	736.	106.	72	Almach	393.0	49.
33	Alioth	82.55	0.42	73	Caph	54.7	0.35
34	Dubhe	122.9	2.2	74	Izar	235.9	8.4
35	Mirfak	506.	13.	75	alpha Lupi	464.6	11.
36	Wezen	1610	300	76	epsilon Centauri	427.5	27.
37	Sargas	300.	41.	77	Dschubba	491.2	66.
38	Kaus Australis	143.3	1.5	78	Larawag	63.7	0.27
39	Avior	605.	47.	79	eta Centauri	305.7	6.0
40	Alkaid	103.9	0.79	80	Merak	84.5	2.5

Notable Star-Pair Angles

Notable star pairs (from the set of the 80 brightest stars listed above) that are close to a multiple of 5° separation. The angles are in degrees.

		<u>Θ</u>	<u>Δθ</u>	<u>defect (%)</u>
Schedar	Caph	5	-0.085	1.7
Betelgeuse	Alnitak	10	0.017	0.17
Capella	Castor	30	-0.023	0.077
Procyon	Mirzam	30	-0.094	0.31
Elnath	Alnilam	30	-0.096	0.32
Alpheratz	Caph	30	0.060	0.20
Aldebaran	Pollux	45	0.013	0.029
Betelgeuse	Algol	50	-0.033	0.066
Alnitak	Naos	50	-0.049	0.098
Pollux	Alioth	60	0.065	0.11
Gacrux	Alphard	60	-0.001	0.002
Regulus	Bellatrix	70	-0.030	0.043
Sirius	Mirfak	80	-0.094	0.12
alpha_Centauri	Regulus	90	0.057	0.063
Vega	Denebola	90	-0.065	0.072
Fomalhaut	Caph	90	0.006	0.007
Deneb	Alnilam	120	0.059	0.049
Menkent	Mintaka	120	0.000	0.000
Sirius	Alphecca	135	-0.089	0.066
Aldebaran	Antares	170	-0.021	0.012

Exeunt

Etymological requests from the ORION Board:

catawampus:

adjective, adverb US informal /ˌkæt.əˈwɑ:m.pəs/

going badly, awkwardly, or in the wrong direction:

- The script is spoiled by its catawampus rhythms and its lack of consistency and plausibility.
- I didn't need this, especially on a morning when everything else had already started out going cattywampus. Dear me, everything has gone catawampus with me this week.
- This is a market where that mantra "buy, don't rent" has been turned catawampus.
- Chagall's work uses geometric shapes, sharp angles, bold colors and catawampus characters.
- From that moment on in the movie things go cattywampus for the squad.

wackadoodle:

adjective US informal /'wæk.əˌdu:..dəl/

strange or silly:

- The idea is exciting for those who believe in it, wackadoodle for those who don't.
- This was considered a wackadoodle conspiracy theory over here.
- America's Founding Fathers certainly did lead interesting, convoluted, not to say completely wackadoodle lives.
- Suddenly, cloning for stem cells is no longer the wackadoodle scheme it once was.
- Had Sigmund Freud not been a writer of genius, would his wackadoodle theories be anything more than a minor footnote?

ORION and TAO (and Obed) General Information (links)

May be found at the following URLs:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tamke-Allan_Observatory

<http://www.orioninc.org/>

<https://orionastronomy.wordpress.com>

<https://www.facebook.com/ORIONAstronomyTN/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/454645124557215>

<https://www.facebook.com/pages/Tamke-Allan%20Observatory/120477734665841>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/?349-Tamke-Allan-Observatory>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/index.htm>

<https://twitter.com/TAOremote>

ORIONastronomy@groups.io

Where is TAO? (Bortle 4)

334 Caney Creek Rd, Rockwood, TN 37854

Gdome = N 35° 49' 56.6", W 84° 37' 03.8"; Alt. 322 m

NE Pad = N 35° 49' 57.4", W 84° 37' 03.1"; Alt. 322 m

Where is Obed? (Bortle 4)

Lilly Bluff Overlook

N 36° 06' 09", W 84° 43' 17"; Alt. 402 m

Nemo Bridge (on the bridge, E bank of Emory River)

N 36° 04' 07", W 84° 39' 43"; Alt. 268 m

Trapezium back issues online, at CERN's zenodo database:

A full CERN zenodo doi url is for example <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8219253>;
a short form, *e.g.* zenodo.org/records/8219253, may also be used.

Vol. 49, Issue 4; Fri 15 Apr 2023:	zenodo.org/records/8219253
Vol. 49, Issue 5; Fri 12 May 2023:	8216818
Vol. 49, Issue 6; Fri 16 Jun 2023:	8030659
Vol. 49, Issue 7; Fri 14 Jul 2023:	8140396
Vol. 49, Issue 8; Fri 18 Aug 2023:	8251302
Vol. 49, Issue 9; Fri 15 Sep 2023:	8336647
Vol. 49, Issue 10; Fri 13 Oct 2023:	8433081
Vol. 49, Issue 11; Fri 17 Nov 2023:	10138151
Vol. 49, Issue 12; Fri 15 Dec 2023:	10382618
Vol. 50, Issue 01; Fri 12 Jan 2024:	10483283
Vol. 50, Issue 02; Fri 16 Feb 2024:	10672625
Vol. 50, Issue 03; Fri 15 Mar 2024:	10822600
Vol. 50, Issue 04; Fri 12 Apr 2024:	10967036
Vol. 50, Issue 05; Fri 10 May 2024:	11176951
Vol. 50, Issue 06; Fri 14 Jun 2024:	11646971
Vol. 50, Issue 07, Fri 12 Jul 2024:	12735071
Vol. 50, Issue 08, Fri 16 Aug 2024:	13333599
Vol. 50, Issue 09, Fri 13 Sep 2024:	13742825
Vol. 50, Issue 10, Fri 11 Oct 2024:	13921735
Vol. 50, Issue 11, Fri 15 Nov 2024:	14171218
Vol. 50, Issue 12, Fri 13 Dec 2024:	14394899
Vol. 51, Issue 01, Fri 10 Jan 2025:	14630165
Vol. 51, Issue 02, Fri 14 Feb 2025:	14873015
Vol. 51, Issue 03, Fri 14 Mar 2025:	15015954
Vol. 51, Issue 04, Fri 11 Apr 2025:	15200349
Vol. 51, Issue 05, Fri 16 May 2025:	15443035
Vol. 51, Issue 06, Fri 13 Jun 2025:	15660329
Vol. 51, Issue 07, Fri 11 Jul 2025:	15865574

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a short form, *e.g.* zenodo.org/records/8219253, may also be used.

Vol. 51, Issue 8; Fri 15 Aug 2025:	zenodo.org/records/16884202
Vol. 51, Issue 9; Fri 12 Sep 2025:	17108361
Vol. 51, Issue 10; Fri 10 Oct 2025:	17316280
Vol. 51, Issue 11; Fri 14 Nov 2025:	17613257

A generic link that lists Trapezium pdf issues (and other ORION documents) starting with the most recent, which does not require a specific zenodo document number, follows:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/rigel/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Fin du journal

Halloween 2025

